

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D2.3 A COMPREHENSIVE STARTUP INCUBATION FRAMEWORK AND TOOLKIT FOR THE EUROPEAN MEDIA SECTOR STARTUP INDUSTRY

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Abstract	This deliverable proposes a comprehensive startup incubation framework and toolkit process for the European media sector startup industry. It takes into account the lessons learned from the first incubation period (OC1) of the STADIEM program and provide critical recommendations for the second incubation program (OC2).
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DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable proposes a comprehensive startup incubation framework and toolkit process for the European media sector startup industry. It takes into account the lessons learned from the first incubation period (OC1) of the STADIEM program and provide critical recommendations for the second incubation program (OC2).

Firstly, the deliverable proposes a five-step approach and canvas-based processes for managers of innovation programs to map and identify the critical variables of the desired program design. Secondly, it complements this approach by providing a comparative overview of different operational models of entrepreneurship programs. It also advocates for a startup supplier model that focuses on delivering tangible business outcomes between the parties rather than purely innovation creation value.

Thirdly, the deliverable focuses on the lessons learned from in consortium survey and in-depth work sessions where jointly areas of improvement such as operational efficiency and consortium communication temperature were raised.

Finally, the deliverable presents an operational structure and mitigation actions along with core program management principles, including an Airtable-based program management tool(kit).

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1 INTRODUCTION

One of the most critical problems faced by innovation and startup-focused entrepreneurship & business development program managers is the selection of the entrepreneurship support and operational model and toolkit, and their impact to surrounding entrepreneurial and business ecosystem, and its operational and competitive sustainability in time.

The entrepreneurial support landscape both globally and in Europe is rich in various incubation and acceleration formats in profit, non-profit, private and corporate dimensions, and features hundreds if not thousands of acceleration or innovation support programs which are all competing for the attention of innovators/startups, as well as investors and corporates as the main stakeholder backers of the business sustainability of those programs. The oversaturation of acceleration offerings in market has led the leading startup and innovation media outlet Sifted even to remark that accelerators “have fallen out of favor because of a lack of results. Only 50% of top [corporate] companies still have their own accelerator program, the rest have transitioned to either a hybrid model where a third party runs part or all of the program” (Palmer 2020).

At the heart of this deliverable is the question - how to design, launch, operate and adapt an ambitious “European media technology scaleups to corporates growth and go to market program” from its initial design as European Commission H2020 funded project to a fully operational, mission driven and mission delivering entity. How and with which kinds of tools this is feasible considering that the accelerator and entrepreneurship support market is oversaturated, startup deal-flow is scarce and drastic impact of the COVID pandemic is felt at all levels from deal-flow to program deployment.

This deliverable attempts to address those large questions as follows. Firstly, it will provide the assessment of the overall trends in the entrepreneurship development programs in Europe and how STADIEM situates to this picture. Secondly, it presents the framework of the STADIEM consortium as well as the implemented program delivery toolkit considering the performance of the program, its operations, and relation to the current state of the European innovation/startup and media ecosystem. Lastly, it will be present some of the key lessons learned, as well as suggestions for adjustments and implementation for the second cohort of the STADIEM program.

The deliverable is written from the perspective of presenting an easy to understand and implementable framework and toolkit guideline that would be easily adaptable and applicable not only for the STADIEM consortium, but also the participating consortium member level, as well as any ecosystem or innovation manager who is aiming to launch their own program.

Chapter 1 gives an overview of the latest trends and principles in how to design an effective startup to corporate entrepreneurship program. Also, it presents the design of the program / framework and its components and processes, including the overview of the process development. Chapter 2 presents the key lessons learned as well as outcomes of a strategic workshop to realign the consortium members prior to the launch of the second cohort of the STADIEM program.

2 CHAPTER 1: HOW TO EFFECTIVELY DESIGN A STARTUP TO CORPORATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP PROGRAM?

2.1 BEYOND ACCELERATORS: CHALLENGES AND TRENDS IMPACTING THE SELECTION ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND INNOVATION CO-CREATION MODEL

In the overall structure of the STADIEM program, work package two (WP2) holds a central position.

Its aims are to create a high-impact, go-to market-focused learning, and scaling framework for the startups/beneficiaries of the project selected from open calls and managed through the two-cycle program.. The framework is focused on providing effective scaling, technology, and business development support for the startups, and is implemented across four participating hubs.

Specifically, the WP2 sets to focus on:

- Analyzing and combining the methodologies of four participating hubs to create a joint, holistic pan-European startup development framework
- Planning and scheduling coaching, mentoring, technology validation and assessment procedures within the hubs and in the consortium to achieve harmonized process across the project
- Acquiring stakeholder (corporates, venture capital, support organizations) feedback to the the framework to address stakeholder needs
- Evaluating and implementing online and offline tools, platforms, and methodologies for executing the framework, monitoring, and assessing results
- Updating the framework and tools/platforms based on lessons learned

How to design and manage an ambitious startup to corporate co-creation and piloting a program to radically innovate the European next-generation media ecosystem – was and is a critical question facing the STADIEM consortium when it launched its first edition of the program and open call (hereafter OC1) to meet the above listed goals for WP2. Although the program goals, objectives, and intervention methods were already outlined in the original proposal, revised and validated during the preparation for the startup of the project and during the months before the launch of the Open Call 1, several important questions remained to be validated. Those questions are described in detail in the deliverable 2.1 filed in M5, but most important of those included:

* How to establish an effective collaborative model between key players of the consortium, considering that each of them serves a critical function in their respective territory and innovation value chain but has a different operational model and focus? What should be the format of this model, especially where there has currently been no comparable program in the market.

* What kinds of tools or toolkits are needed to manage an ambitious program in a hybrid environment where most of the program delivery and monitoring needs to take place online due to the COVID19 pandemic?

* How to implement those toolkits effectively and integrate lessons learned, especially after the first year of the program?

TABLE 1 : OVERVIEW OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP PROGRAM FORMATS IMPLEMENTED BY THE CONSORTIUM MEMBERS

Name of the Hub	Territories	Operational Format	Key verticals	Focus areas
VRT	Belgium, mainland Europe	Corporation, Public Broadcaster	Public broadcasting related innovation	Corporate innovation, sandboxing, European R&D & innovation boosting program
Next Media Accelerator (NMA)	Germany, mainland Europe	Accelerator	Publishing related innovation	Corporate innovation, acceleration programs, R&D & Innovation boosting programs
Media City Bergen	Norway, Scandinavia	Cluster	Media innovation at large	Cluster focused innovation programs, European R&D the Innovation boosting programs
Storytek / Exit Academy	Estonia, worldwide	Innovation and Venture building studio	Mediatech innovation, exit and investments	Exit focused mature scaleup upskilling, boosting of exit capacity and investment capacity

Steps in launching startup-focused entrepreneurship program

FIGURE 1: PROCESS OVERVIEW FOR LAUNCHING STARTUP-FOCUSED ENTREPRENEURSHIP PROGRAM

The following table and figure give an overview of the critical milestones in using the Agile Service Design process in updating and revising the operational model, components and processes, framework, and toolkit in the period of M1-M18 of the project.

Step	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5	Step 6
Key action	Identify the core variables of the program	Select the operational model	Design the program components and processes	Deploy & implement the program	Analyse, learn, adapt, and restart if necessary	Adjustments agreed and implemented to the program
Time period / phase	Preparation of the project	Preparation of the project, revised M1-12	Preparation of the project, revised M1-12	Revised M5-M12	Implemented M8-12	From M13 onwards

TABLE 2 : THE REVISION PROCESS OF THE OPERATIONAL MODEL, FRAMEWORK AND TOOLKIT FOR THE STADIEM PROGRAM

FIGURE 2: OVERVIEW OF THE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS OF STADIEM FRAMEWORK AND TOOLKIT VERSION 2

2.1.1 Step 1: Identifying core variables, components and processes

As mentioned above, a way of mapping the core variables of a new program, and revisiting the key components of an existing entrepreneurship program can be developed using the **Startup Program Design Canvas (SPDC) method**. This method and canvas was developed and utilized by consortium partner Storytek for its in house work for designing innovation programs for various clients both in the public and private sector. In the context of STADIEM, utilizing this method assists to reiterate the key elements of the program's framework and toolkit prior the launch of OC2 of STADIEM.

The canvas helps program managers to map the positioning and core parameter of the entrepreneurship program, especially for Steps 1 and 2 (components and operational method), by helping to identify the following variables:

- What industry/vertical will the program be targeting or operating in (general or specific)?
- What is the primary value that the program unlocks?
- Who are the primary beneficiaries, and at what stage of startup development are they?
- Who are the main stakeholders?
- What are the territories the program serves / beneficiaries are eligible for?
- What are the primary outcomes of the program?
- What resources (financial/investment and program deployment) are available for the program?

The following figures (Figures 3 and 4) present the canvas format and the key mapped outcomes for the STADIEM program.

Startup / Entrepreneurship Program design canvas

Core Value Proposition What is the main value the program unlocks?	Industry / Vertical What industry / vertical the program Focuses on?	Territories What are the territories the program covers and/or participants come from?
Key Beneficiaries Who are main beneficiaries and what stage of the life cycle are they?	Key Stakeholders Who are main stakeholders? What do they gain from the program?	
Main Outcomes What are the main outcomes of the program?	Existing Resources What are existing resources to manage/run the program	

FIGURE 3: STARTUP / ENTREPRENEURSHIP PROGRAM DESIGN CANVAS

Startup / Entrepreneurship Program design canvas

Core Value Proposition What is the main value the program unlocks? EU financed, zero equity startup to corporate piloting & growth booster. Market best dealflow with up to €150K support.	Industry / Vertical What industry / vertical the program Focuses on? Media and content industries With focus on next gen media solutions.	Territories What are the territories the program covers and/or participants come from? European Union and Horizon Europe eligible countries.
Key Beneficiaries Who are main beneficiaries and what stage of the life cycle are they? Expert validated scaleups and EU (Media) corporates.	Key Stakeholders Who are main stakeholders? What do they gain from the program? EU Media Corporates: Access to dealflow / innovation pilots. Investors: Upskiling and biz dev for portfolios Stadiem consortium: Access to startups, Methodologies, finance, Learnings	
Main Outcomes What are the main outcomes of the program? At least 80 scaleups in the program, 8pilots concluded. Growth of innovation, dealflow And startup/corporate network.	Existing Resources What are existing resources to manage/run the program Horizon Europe financing, access to at least 4 ecosystems through hubs, corporate, mentoring and business development networks,	

FIGURE 4: STARTUP / ENTREPRENEURSHIP PROGRAM DESIGN CANVAS WITH MAPPING OF KEY COMPONENTS OF THE STADIEM PROGRAM

Notably, compared to the widespread Business Model Canvas, the SPDC misses the mapping of a business model criteria. It does so for two main reasons. First, a business model approach is not well applicable in publicly funded innovation or / entrepreneurship development projects (such as Horizon Europe or other national/local level funded projects) due to the non-profit

nature of the funding. For example, a consortium-based project, where vast differences exist between consortium members' business and legal statutes, does not easily allow a business model-based operational format, i.e., taking equity from beneficiaries' stock pool, co-investing, selling co-created services during the period of funding, and so forth.

Secondly, everyday evidence from the market, as well as work on the performance of business acceleration services (i.e. as discussed in Sifted EU and elsewhere), has demonstrated that if the program does not operate directly as investment-based, the business model of the program will evolve over a long period and will constitute of a combination of various models including investments, consultation, scouting as services and so forth.

Lastly, and most importantly, in order for a startup-focused program to be successful and competitive in the ecosystem, it primarily needs to deliver a clear and unique value proposition for its beneficiaries, stakeholders, and the ecosystem. A significant academic inquiry into the key success factors of business acceleration services (KSF) by Bagnoli et al. (2020)¹ also supports this argument by indicating the prevalence of a value proposition in academic literature conversing business acceleration services. It is also noting that "the presence of a clear value proposition is a relevant indicator to determine the success of an accelerator...the success of an accelerator is not only determined by the value delivered to its customers, but also by the value delivered to its partners, like alumni, mentors, and investors, and to society, i.e., the other actors of the ecosystem in which it operates" (Bagnoli et al 2020).

Thus, starting the program design through identifying the value proposition and mapping the parameters, for examples by using the Startup Program Design Canvas approach can improve the the positioning and success of the startup-focused program in the larger entrepreneurship support ecosystem. Going through the mapping exercise also helps the program designers play with the variables to ensure hitting the mark in two criteria that define the program's success in the long term. First, provide a high volume, quality, performance of applying startups (so-called deal flow) in a highly competitive environment (for a more extended discussion of the need to ensure deal flow see below). Second, attract and build a high-quality stakeholder and business partner network, which is vital for ensuring the growth of the startups within the program and ensuring the long-term sustainability of the entrepreneurship program itself.

¹ Bagnoli, Massaro, & Ruzza. (n.d.). Business models for accelerators: a structured literature review. *Journal of Business* . <https://journals.aau.dk/index.php/JOBM/article/view/3032>

2.2 STEP 2: MAPPING THE OPERATIONAL MODEL

After the core variables of the program are mapped, the program designer should proceed to select the operational model with a variety of choices ranging from accelerators and incubators to corporate venturing (CVC) and hybrid models. What to choose, and what was the model suitable model for STADIEM?

Startup accelerators and incubators are undoubtedly the most popular and widely applied entrepreneurship and innovation-driven business development operational models in Europe. Even more, accelerators and incubators form the basic DNA of the current innovation ecosystem globally as "they create a pipeline of companies that other investors can invest in; thus, the accelerators' value created for investors is having the mechanisms to scout and filter for talent in place" (Wallenius 2018). The working principles, efficiencies, upsides, and drawbacks and their impact have been investigated widely academically (see Cohen & Hochberg 2014, Wallenius 2018, and others)².

However, in recent years, the accelerator/incubator model, both at personal and corporate ownership levels, has come under increasing scrutiny for the following challenges:

- over-saturation in the market. For example, the Global Accelerator Network (GAN) alone has 122 accelerator members, with 17 accelerator members in Europe. Yet, in reality, the market is dominated by a few super accelerators (Y Combinator, Techstars, Seedcamp), a small range of corporate super accelerators (Disney, Boeing ATI), acceleration service providers/studios, European policy-focused acceleration providers (EIT), vertically focused players, and the rest of hundreds of smaller acceleration providers in European members states.
- fierce competition for high-quality deal flow. All of the above-mentioned acceleration providers are competing for the high-quality deal flow to their programs, especially for late-stage startups. According to major Startup focused media outlet Sifted, corporations alone "will typically look at 1,000-5,000 startups each year, whittling them down to a shortlist of around 200. Of those, around 10-20% will go on to do a pilot project with a company, and typically around 20 might go on a full commercial deal". Thus, competing on a generic acceleration program offering in Europe, both in generic vertical and dedicated industry, is difficult as there are not enough mature startups.
- long term, low viability business model. Accelerators tend to operate on the equity-based model, taking a % of the startup's shares with the hope of monetizing from startup exits (buyouts) or IPOs. While Europe is increasingly producing unicorn startups (see the latest State of European Tech report), only a fraction of startups will reach a profitable business operation, let alone exit, M&A, or IPO. Thus the Startup equity-driven business model, in

² Wallenius, J. (2018). *Long-term impacts of startup accelerators* [aaltodoc.aalto.fi]. <https://aaltodoc.aalto.fi/handle/123456789/32569>

Cohen, S., Fehder, D. C., Hochberg, Y. V., & Murray, F. (2019). The design of startup accelerators. *Research Policy*, 48(7), 1781–1797. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2019.04.003>

reality, has low sustainability forcing managers to fund programs through grants, scouting investments, corporate sponsorships, or alternative models.

Thus it becomes clear that in the highly saturated, deal-flow competitive, and business model risky environment, an ambitious startup to corporate program needs seeks either a complementary model to accelerators/incubators or tailor a custom model/custom positioning to achieve efficiency and viability in the market.

Cohen et al. in the comprehensive assessment of different entrepreneurship models have developed a valuable approach to identify the benefits and drawbacks of different operational models for startup & entrepreneurship development programs. The table below summarizes the key findings and positions of STADIEM vis a vis other models.

	Accelerator	Incubator	VC Investor	Corporate Venturing / Corporate Accelerator	STADIEM Positioning
Duration	3-6 months	1-5 years	Ongoing	Ongoing	1 year per cohort
Cohorts	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Business model	Investment / non-profit	Rent / non-profit, co-creation	Investment	In house value creation	In network value creation, investment
Selection frequency	Competitive, cyclical	Non competitive	Competitive, ongoing	Non competitive, strategic	Competitive, cyclical, strategic
Venture Stage	Early	Early or late	Early, scaling, late	Early	Scaling
Education offered	Seminars	Ad hoc, HR, Legal	None	Tailor made, needs based, in house-external	Tailor made, needs based, in house-external
Venture location	Usually on site	On-site	Off site	On site	Hybrid
Mentorship	Intense	Minimal, tactical	As needed, by investor	As needed, in house	As needed, in house
Financing allocated	Occasional, equity based	Occasional, equity based	Regular, equity taken	Regular, co ownership	Regular, grant based
Focus	Product development	Business model validation	Scaling	New products/services creation, scaling	Scaling, piloting

TABLE 3 : COMPARISON OF VARIOUS STARTUP & ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT MODELS AND POSITIONING OF STADIEM. ADAPTED FROM COHEN, HOCHBERG. 2014. "ACCELERATING STARTUPS: THE SEED ACCELERATOR PHENOMENON". SSRN JOURNAL, MARCH 2014, 1-16.

As can be seen from the table, and to meet its goals, STADIEM has decided to adapt a hybrid operation that focuses on startup to corporate piloting. The hybrid model draws from the long-term duration of incubators, adopts a cohort-based, competitive approach to accelerators, selects beneficiaries at later stages coinciding with the VC-driven system, and focuses on scaling, which is at the heart of corporate venturing. By merging success components from each of the above-described models, the STADIEM proposes a new model for startup

corporate co-creation – a startup supplier mode program model, introduced by Kurpjuweit & Wagner³.

The pioneering work in identifying an effective startup to corporate scouting program model has been done by Kurpjuweit & Wagner (2020) in their article "Startup Supplier Programs: A New Model for Managing Corporate-Startup Partnerships."

In work, the authors argue that "Startup supplier programs are outside-in programs that enable firms to get access to innovations that increase the competitiveness of products or productivity of processes by engaging with startups based upon supplier relationships." Specifically, they point out that while accelerator programs might often have conflicting goals, i.e. "ranging from gaining access to a startup's technology over exploring ideas, attracting talent, or helping startups to set up their businesses," startup supplier program in contrast "have a clear focus on selecting, integrating, and developing promising startups as suppliers by facilitating direct collaboration with their internal departments, business units, or divisions" (Kurpjuweit & Wagner 2020).

For the corporates, participating in a startup supplier program "shows a corporate's willingness to become a startup's customer," whereas for the startup, it "retains its independence, which allows collaborations with other established firms and keeps the startup agile" (ibid.).

STADIEM, by its program design, applies and advocates for a startup supplier program operation model precisely for the above-mentioned reasons:

- The program scouts beneficiaries from a very large pool of startups (approximately 400 applicants in total over two open calls)
- It develops a shortlist of target startups that match the criteria or deliver value to the corporate via a piloting program
- It supports the startup to corporate collaboration through a clear value proposition-driven program format through its four stages.
- Through the pilot-focused design, it encourages the corporate to become the customer of the startup whilst the startup remains independent in its agile development process.

Interestingly, the startup supplier program model has been also making rounds in the innovation development communities for the past year, whereas its popularity can be attributed to the challenges facing the widespread accelerator/incubator format.

For example, prominent startup and venture capital platform Sifted in its trends overview of startup to corporate collaboration advocated over accelerators either a venture building model (the corporation itself builds startups) or a structured scouting program model noting that "All

³ Kurpjuweit, S., & Wagner, S. M. (2020). Startup Supplier Programs: A New Model for Managing Corporate-Startup Partnerships. In *California Management Review* (Vol. 62, Number 3, pp. 64–85). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0008125620914995>

the leading companies...have some structured program to scout startups that they might want to work with...whittling them down to a shortlist of around 200. Of those, around 10-20% will go on to do a pilot project with a company, and typically around 20 might go on a full commercial deal"⁴.

The startup supplier operational model also supports and validates the original assumptions of the project, as well as reinforces the original framework design inspired by NESTA's "Startup to corporation collaboration strategies"⁵ as well as Schrage's⁶ five-stage process for a startup to corporate collaboration consisting of Derisking, Applying "Less is more" principle, Aligning any insights gained to KPI improvements, Planning for follow up, "next experiments" and Actively promoting positive learnings and outcomes. Both of those principles are described in more detail in deliverable 2.1 of the project. Figure 6 presents STADIEM's operational model as a startup supplier program.

FIGURE 5: STADIEM PROGRAM DESIGN AS "STARTUP SUPPLIER" PROGRAM FOR NEXT GENERATION MEDIA INNOVATIONS IN EUROPE

⁴ Palmer, M. (2021, December 14). *What's hot and what's not in corporate innovation*. Sifted. <https://sifted.eu/articles/hot-not-corporate-innovation-report/>

⁵ Mocker, V., Bielli, S., & Haley, C. (n.d.). *A GUIDE TO SUCCESSFUL CORPORATE-STARTUP COLLABORATIONS*. Retrieved May 30, 2022, from https://media.nesta.org.uk/documents/winning-_together-june-2015.pdf

⁶ Schrage, M. (2018, May 30). The Right Way for an Established Firm to Do an Innovation Pilot with a Startup. *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/2018/05/the-right-way-for-an-established-firm-to-do-an-innovation-pilot-with-a-startup>

The following table (Table 4), adapted from Kurpjuweit & Wagner, describes the key elements of a startup supplier program and presents STADIEM's properties as a hybrid version of the operational model. The matching clearly validates STADIEM's compatibility with the model, as well the benefits that the operational model brings to the stakeholders.

	Features	Corporate Accelerators / Corporate Venturing	Startup Supplier Programs	Stadium Stadium hybrid venturing / startup supplier program
Strategic Scope	Program Objective	Pursue multiple goals such as attracting talent, exploring ideas, closing technological gaps, and rejuvenating corporate culture	Select, integrate, and develop startups as suppliers to integrate entrepreneurial innovations into the corporate's core business	Select, integrate, and develop startups to pilot entrepreneurial innovations and integrate into the corporate's core business
	Value proposition to startup	Multiple: help to establish a business, develop a business model, funding, access to corporate resources, mentoring	Become an official supplier	Become an official supplier/acquire corporate as client and (learn how to) scale in the market
	Startup type	Early stage	Mid-/later stage	Mid-/later stage
Program Content	Project focus	Development of a first prototype	Customization of the startup's technology according to specific requirements	Customization of the startup's business processes & technology according to specific requirements
	Application procedure	Usually cohorts, scheduled application dates	Continuously	Cohorts with application dates, then continuously in program
	Duration	Fixed, typically 3-6 months	Flexible, typically 1-6 months	Flexible, up to 18 months
	Organisational setup	Divers: Internal, in cooperation with other established firms, or together with a professional provider (e.g., Techstars)	Internal	Internal, with direct piloting development / co creation projects with startups
	Number of startups	Limited by the number of relationship managers	Unlimited, since the main contact is from the business unit	Unlimited by the number of applications, one selected for final pilot
	Main contact	Innovation manager from corporate accelerator	Manager from core business, innovation managers only support the collaboration	Manager from core business involved in pilot, innovation managers only support the collaboration
	End of program	Demo day with a pitch in front of VCs, business angels, the media, and corporate executives	Pitch in front of decision makers of business units	Pitch in front of decision makers of business unit (pilot responsible) and the Stadium investment committee and a demo day
Provided Resources	Financial	Fix amount of money, often in form of equity investments	Flexible payment which accounts as revenues	Flexible, upper limit payment which accounts as revenues towards completed business development & pilot advancement deliverables

	Education	Startup related (lean startup, funding, pitch training, legal basics)	Corporate related (industry specifics, purchasing process)	Corporate business development related (industry specifics, purchasing process, piloting process, legal etc)
	Networking	Internally within corporate and externally with alumni, entrepreneurs, investors	Decision makers in customer business units; managers from relevant functions (purchasing, SCM, legal), selected established suppliers	Decision makers in customer business units; externally with entrepreneurs, investors, clients
	Product-related	Prototyping facilities, co-working space	Testing and production facilities	Testing and production, piloting related facilities

TABLE 4 : COMPARISON OF CORPORATE ACCELERATORS, STARTUP SUPPLIERS AND THE STADIEM PROGRAM CHARACTERISTICS. KURPJUWEIT, S., & WAGNER, S. M. (2020). STARTUP SUPPLIER PROGRAMS: A NEW MODEL FOR MANAGING CORPORATE-STARTUP PARTNERSHIPS. IN CALIFORNIA MANAGEMENT REVIEW (VOL. 62, NUMBER 3, PP. 64–85).

2.3 STEP 3: DESIGNING THE PROCESSES AND TOOLS OF THE PROGRAM

Once the initial assumptions and components of the program have been mapped, and the operational model has been selected, the process moves to the design of the process and tools to manage the program.

Once the initial assumptions and components of the program have been mapped, and the operational model has been selected, the process moves to the design of the process and tools to manage the program.

The original processes and tools for the STADIEM program were described in detail in the original proposal, as well as the deliverable 2.1. However, shortly the processes and tools consist of the following components:

STADIEM’s core processes

FIGURE 6: STADIEM'S CORE PROCESSES

The delivery and assessment toolkit chosen for STADIEM was based on the best practices found in each of the hubs. The consortium consists of Europe's finest accelerators and innovation clusters in media tech, and it is, therefore, most sustainable to utilize the experiences, methods, and tools. The main principles of the toolkit were as follows:

- The toolkit will consist of components that ensure that information can be collected, stored, and shared.
- Sustainability is an important aspect of STADIEM, to build on the best practices already in place in each of the hubs and its network, as well establish a reusable toolkit for the future. Tools in use by consortium members were prioritized rather than embarking on a broad acquisition from a number of suppliers.
- The consortium sees it as far more useful to utilize the experiences that the hubs have had over many years rather than using STADIEM as a test box for a completely new set of tools.
- Disadvantages of the new set of tools include the lack of synergies compared to what is used daily by the hubs; it could take away focus, lead to increased risk in implementation, and a risk that hubs do not use software licenses that are already in use, but instead incur new costs.
- Emphasis is also placed on avoiding proprietary or self-developed solutions, which require a cost of learning and implementing a unique solution, and risks associated with a lack of long-term support - both by the hub representatives, startup teams, and experts.
- Since the development framework does not impose a single method or structure for every hub, the toolkit should not be absolutely indicative either.
- Because of the Covid-19 situation, with its travel restrictions, there was a focus in this work on identifying requirements needed for a fully digital toolkit.

From November to December 2022, STADIEM consortium members from MCB / VIS conducted a review of framework delivery and assessment processes tools and platforms that had been adopted and started implemented. This was as part of Task 2.4, where the purpose was to update this toolkit with the goal of optimizing various communication, scheduling, and feedback processes.

The process synchronized with the larger assessment of STADIEM's framework and the feedback of the consortium (presented in section 2) undertaken by consortium members Storytek and Exit Academy. The assessment confirmed the suitability, relevance, and operational quality of the initial framework but also marked two larger shifts.

Firstly, the transformation from an open framework model to a startup supplier framework

Secondly, the need to optimize and consolidate the program management processes from a range of various tools into a centrally managed system.

The following chapter describes in detail the improvements that were initiated immediately after the survey was completed and discussed among the consortium members.

3 CHAPTER 2: DESIGNING AND IMPLEMENTING THE PROGRAM FRAMEWORK AND TOOLKIT

While the first chapter of this deliverable looked at the overarching principles of how to design an effective startup to corporate entrepreneurship program, the following chapter looks at the actual design process, platform selection, and consortium feedback to the process to map and implement lessons learned.

When various tools were chosen to take care of and support the framework and assessment, the intention was to build on known cloud-based solutions without the need for tailoring or dedicated developer resources. Airtable was selected because the toolkit is, therefore, very flexible, where new services and tables in the main database can easily be set up or changed if needed.

During the first phases of Open Call 1, the consortium's HUBs gained experience regarding the use of the tools and methods that were chosen. The task 2.4 lead, MCB, conducted a round of interviews where members from each hub provided feedback. It was identified that improvements could be made in certain areas and processes.

When the survey was conducted among the consortium members, based on their own experiences and feedback from startups, the following were highlighted as areas for improvement:

- Communication channels between HUBs and startups need to be improved.
- Program management-related information that needs to be centralized and documented could also have been retrieved more easily, goes through too many steps or ends up as stand-alone, unlinked documents.
- The tools could be simplified with the better onboarding process.

3.1 STEP 4: DESIGN AND IMPLEMENT THE PROGRAM AND TOOLKIT

In connection with an adaptation of the framework in STADIEM, the necessary adaptations were made to make the delivery and assessment toolkit correspondingly optimized.

The main measures were not necessarily only about changes associated with the technology platform. As through Open Call 1, several experiences were made that were often necessary to take manually but which can now be automated or made more efficient. It can also be about changes in routines more than technology.

The measures that were set to be implemented for Version 2 for the toolkit are:

- To streamline the communication is the main priority. As the respective in the HUBs who have been responsible for main communication with the startups sits with valuable experiences (such as their email responses, forms, and the like), this can now be put into a more suitable presentation and data collection. Where appropriate, this could allow a move of the information flow from "push sending" to "pull receive" in short: be able to remove a lot of heavy email correspondence:
- Based on experiences in Open Call 1, where a template (i.e., a digital form, canvas) would have been more appropriate than the chosen format, such templates will be created if

necessary. This can also ensure increased reuse of sustainable, valuable toolkit components outside of the STADIEM life cycle.

- Establish overviews, FAQs, and similar, made such that the individual can look it up themselves, rather than asking individually.
- Better ensure that information shared by one HUB also can be reused by all HUBs.
- Requested information from both HUBs as startups can be entered directly into the database through forms instead of separate documents. Such effort can remove manual tasks.
- A simple ticketing system (not a full Customer Relationship Management (CRM) system) will be tested to make sure questions from startups can be recorded, and answers shared more generally.
- Optimize the joint acceleration management toolkit platform to make it harmonize with any changes in or optimization of the overarching framework of STADIEM
- Technological integration needs or change of technology. If any new tools are needed or existing to be replaced, this will be reviewed as a part of the upcoming work (see below). Any changes made will have to be based on specified needs and according to any financial impacts.
- In order to be ahead of any Covid 19-related restrictions, which may pose challenges for STADIEM's tasks, it is important to follow the development of the spread of infection closely. When it was identified that the digital match phase required in Open Call 1, was not sufficient to engage media corporates, the consortium must be prepared to work out new, engaging solutions that can still give the desired effect and involvement. The HUBs will then need to speak with their respective network about what is expected.
- The consortium will identify innovative solutions to realize an engaging, digital Match Phase.

3.2 THE FRAMEWORK AND TOOLKIT DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS

In January 2022, MCB/VIS and Storytek/Exit Academy held a two-day intensive work session in Bergen with a focus on improving communication channels, identifying the core features of a centralized program management platform, prototyping the platform, validating the features with the consortium and agreeing on an implementation roadmap. It was agreed between the consortium that the implementation would focus on the period after M18 to coincide with the start of the OC2, which would give an opportunity to fully onboard startups from the perspective of a clean slate.

During the workshop, the following core features of the toolkit were identified and prototyped:

Feature	Description
Stadiem Calendar	A cross program calendar that gives an overview of the OC1 and OC2 phases, key dates, responsibilities.

Feature	Description
Issue Tracker	An issue tracking form that allows startups to file issues or requests via centralized form to eliminate email and allow for joint responses.
Announcement board	An announcement board for key events, activities and deadlines.
Collaborative Task Tracker	A task tracker mapping cross consortium tasks and responsibilities
Activity Tracker	A tracker to map Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation activities
Files gateway	A joint gateway to the file repositories of the project
Startup database	A database of all beneficiary startups

TABLE 5 : DESCRIPTION OF THE FUNCTIONALITIES OF STADIEM TOOLKIT VERSION 2

The updated toolkit was decided to deliver in the form of a centralized database built around the service Airtable. The database was set up to easily receive information and then distribute it to the right recipients. Setting up a workflow in Airtable is relatively as easy as creating an online spreadsheet or similar. The advantage of getting it right into the database is that we create a better overview of where the information is and that it can easily be shared through predefined dashboards or interfaces.

During the development period, the focus was to implement more time getting tools that run directly on Airtable and automating these. In this way, the need for manual transmission of information was reduced, and it should be easier to find back to shared information in the various dashboards that have been set up. The fact that several emails and individual follow-up emails must be sent are some of the things that were addressed as well. This is because it was perceived by the consortium members as time-consuming and a possible source of the incorrect or skewed distribution of information.

It is not the case that the processes and "light-applications" and workflows set up in Airtable should replace all use of email sending, nor the use of documents or spreadsheets. The goal was to have better control over where these documents are stored and how they can be shared with the right recipient.

Probably one of the reasons for a rather fragmented workflow in the first cycle, is that better guidance and testing in Airtable could have been done more and earlier. Being able to lower the threshold for setting up your own workflows in Airtable and use it fully as a tool among the consortium's members, and not just a few, is, therefore, one of the goals going forward.

A user manual that is continuously updated becomes one of the tools for better success with this.

The following table summarizes the benefits of utilizing this type of database tool as a process management solution.

Function	Purpose
----------	---------

Airtable Interface	To create dashboards where you can find an overview of information, as the Startup Homepage where announcements, the issue tracker and often used documents are among the features listed. To create searchable views and a collaborative task overview is example of interfaces made available.
Airtable forms	A way to easy receive information into the database. Forms may be used to receive information without giving direct read or write access to the database. A use case is when startups will report a problem, send in their assignment reports, or for the consortium to easy set up a new event in the calendar.
Airtable calendar	The calendar and timeline features built into is a powerful way to align all dates and periods in STADIEM. The calendar can filter information or present the dates and periods either as a calendar or grouped as timelines. The calendar is one database, but filters make sure that the right information is handed out for the right target group.
Airtable automation	This feature gives a lot of flexibility to automate the information workflow. One example is to be able to post a new message into Slack, or send a reminder-email when a new announcement has been posted. The calendar can also be synced with calendars in Outlook, Google, Apple Calendar or similar.
Airtable Tables & Views	The tables are the main component in Airtables, this is where the information is stored. The tables has full trackability, so if any changes are made the history is stored as well. There are multiple views inside the table as well, like a gallery view or Kanban view.

TABLE 6 : FUNCTIONALITY BREAKDOWN OF TOOLKIT IN AIRTABLE

3.3 PROGRESS PLAN AND WORK

The progress for the mentioned optimizations of delivery and assessment toolkit was implemented so that they are available in advance of each phase of the upcoming Open Call 2. As adaptations and optimizations are based on experiences made through Open Call 1, it is appropriate to adapt continuously but in advance of the start of each phase. The implementation might require optimization of routines, as well as technology.

To ensure a more comprehensive and unified framework, more of the work with the toolkit will also be organized in groups consisting of two or more HUBs. The work will be done in dedicated workshops but also through even better utilization of the unique expertise that sits with individual members of the consortium. The work of adapting and optimizing the framework is coordinated by Media City Bergen and their incubation partner VIS Mediacube.

The deadline to align needs in accordance with the overarching framework was set for 28 February 2022, with subsequent updates planned at least once per phase.

3.4 SCREENSHOTS FROM THE STADIEM TOOLKIT VERSION 2 IN AIRTABLE

FIGURE 7: SCREENSHOTS OF CALENDAR AND COLLECTIVE TASK BREAKDOWN IN THE STADIEM TOOLKIT VERSION 2

St Startup Homepage / Startup General Edit Share feedback Share

STARTUP HOMEPAGE - Open Call 1

Latest announcements from STADIEM TEAM

Dummy - Extended deadline

Dummy - Extended deadline The deadline for filling out the forms has been extended until Friday the 13th.

No bad luck.

Created By: Kristian Bruarøy Created: 1.2.2022 16:19 Read more at <http://stadiem.eu>

[All announcements](#)

Issue reporting

If you have any questions or issues where assistance from the STADIEM team is needed, please report through the Issue Inquiry form (link below). We collect and share relevant questions in our FAQ.

[ISSUE INQUIRY FORM](#)

LATEST FROM THE FAQ:

Dummy: Where do I find the document

Original Inquiry
I was wondering where I can find the document for filling in my application?

<p>Solution</p> <p>Here is the link: https://linktodocument.com</p>	<p>Solution Attachment</p> <p>No attachments</p>
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[COMPLETE FAQ DATABASE](#)

Relevant Documents and Reports

□	📄 File name	📄 File description	📎 Attachments
1	DEVELOP PHASE - INFORMATION	Overview of expectations and obligations in the Development Phase.	
2	PROGRESS REPORT TEMPLATE DEVELOP PHASE	Periodic technical and financial report template to be submitted.	
2 records			

[ALL RELEVANT DOCUMENTS AND TEMPLATES](#)

Calendar

Grouped by: Event type

Quarter: February 7 - March 7 - April 18

- ▼ Deadline / Due-date
- ▼ Meeting

FIGURE 8: SCREENSHOT FROM STARTUP LANDING PAGE FROM STADIEM TOOLKIT VERSION 2

4 LESSONS LEARNED AND IMPLEMENTATION OF THE TOOLKIT

4.1 STEP 5: ANALYZE, LEARN, ADAPT, AND RESTART IF NECESSARY

The last step in designing and implementing a startup to corporate entrepreneurship program is to execute a continuous learning loop to gather data, learn, adapt and restart the process if necessary.

In the case of the STADIEM program, the process of the framework has been adopted at the following intervals.

- **systemic updates** executed at major timeline points of the program (i.e., OC1, OC2, in between phases) - focused on large shifts or updates
- **regular updates** executed in cadence with the weekly/biweekly consortium meetings

During the period between M12 - M18, WP2 leader Storytek and partner MCB undertook a wide exercise to analyze the performance of existing processes and tools (the latter described in Chapter 1) to map key issues, opportunities, and improvement points.

Specifically, a two-day framework and alignment work session was held with additional engaging expertise from internationally celebrated innovation and service design studio Ghost Company to understand key issues, processes, and action points for the operational framework and its implementation. The work session was held on the How space facilitation platform that allows vast gathering of participant input combined with voting and AI-powered tools to achieve rapid consensus and decision making.

The work session focused on understanding the alignment around the mission of STADIEM, history and expectations, core stakeholders and their needs, operational model between audience, network, and community, and process improvements that should be directed

towards improving internal processes the framework, and the corresponding toolkit. The following section describes the key findings from the work session.

FIGURE 9: A LANDING PAGE WITH THE WORK SESSION STRUCTURE ON HISTORY, NEEDS, STAKEHOLDERS, COMMUNITY AND PROCESS DEVELOPMENT FOR THE STADIEM TOOLKIT VERSION 2

4.2 KEY FINDINGS FROM THE FRAMEWORK SYSTEMIC UPDATE WORKSESSION

The first task of the work session was to jointly identify the mission and focus of the STADIEM program. Where the participants came up with the following statements.

STADIEM is a program where small and medium-sized companies get guidance, connections, and funding to help develop new media solutions together with larger media companies. For this, we connect startups and industry corporates to collaborate on innovation projects.

As we can see, the mission statement aligns well with the framework of the startup supplier program, which also focuses on delivering value to the startup and corporate through a well-tailored and scouted program logic.

Regarding the long-term dreams and outcomes of the program deployment, the consortium agreed that the best joint outcome would be the following:

Having the startups and scale-ups from the project succeed and thrive so that Stadiem becomes a good example in H2020 projects, as a project that had effective results in empowering the media ecosystem in the EU.

The deliverables in work package five specifically address the success ratio of the participating startups in OC1. However, it can be mentioned here that the program delivered its outcomes

with a strong success ratio, with one startup exiting the program due to acquisition from a corporate (partly enabled by STADIEM) and several others engaging in co-creation with high-level corporates.

FIGURE 10: THE ANNOUCEMENT OF HIGH CALIBER PILOT BETWEEN OC1 STARTUP FILMCHAIN AND LEADING GERMAN FILM DISTRIBUTOR ALAMODE

4.3 EVALUATION OF THE EXISTING PROGRAM STRUCTURE AND FRAMEWORK

When evaluating the existing program structure and framework, the majority of the consortium members communicated that no significant changes should be made nor are necessary to the program cadence, format, planned outcomes, and financial/structural planning established in the original project proposal, continuing with a structure that respects the original proposal but leaves ample of room for the hubs to exercise their competences. The detailed approach and the process leading to this approach have been documented in deliverable 2.1 (D2.1):

The first step in the work session was to identify expectations and hiccups. The majority of the consortium members communicated that the expectations of the program are met somewhat, with a minority indicating that they were met fully or not at all.

FIGURE 11: RESULTS FROM THE WORKSESSION

The main hiccup points that were mentioned were high overhead and management requirements for an agile innovation program, inability to conduct face-to-face meetings and events, slow response of corporate (in the early phases of the program) as well as very intensive timeline pressures for execution.

The table summarizes three key focus areas where improvements were requested by the consortium members, along with recommendations for action.

Requested changes	Actions
Better communication and engagement with the corporates	1:1 sessions with the corporates, involvement of the corporates in the decision making from Integrate to Pilot
Optimize project management to reduce overhead	Develop and implement a more effective toolkit (at Airtable)
Utilize learnings from the program	Build more 1:1 time between the hubs, especially face to face interactions

TABLE 7 : OVERVIEW OF REQUESTED CHANGES EMERGING FROM THE WORK SESSION WITH PROPOSED MITIGATION ACTIONS

The second step of the worksession focused on remapping and identifying stakeholders and their needs. Regarding the stakeholders and their needs, the work session identified the following stakeholders and their needs.

Stakeholder	Needs	Exceeding expectations	Actions for the consortium
Startups	A qualitative program that addresses startups innovation/growth needs with assuring qualitative matches with corporates. Access to corporates to improve their product and access to better skills and knowledge how to work with corporates.	A smooth sailing STADIEM program, a program that does not need European funding (in the future), being a translator between startups and corporates to achieve successful exits	We manage an optimized pipeline, feedback loop and process in communicating with the startups to understand and help them to realize their needs. We will work collaboratively to provide the best programme possible.
Corporates	Getting access to amazing technology and innovations. Amazing innovations with cheaper cost. Innovative solutions.	Bring them easy and fluid innovation. Making Stadiem results broadly accessible. Amazing dealflow.	We find the best projects to invest that bring added value to the media industry. We will provide media corporates with a low-threshold opportunity to co-create new and needed solutions with startups.
The EU	A good European media market supported by good trustworthy technology. Media solutions which helps towards creating a sustainable democracy. Reliable media.	Building a pan-European media platform. Better visibility for EU media platform. Measurable KPI: compared to EU's standard corporate-startup pilots failure rate of 70%, STADIEM's startups will have only 10% failure rate.	We communicate and increase visibility about the excellency of our scale-ups and shed lights on how we help develop reliable media. We will support and boost startups that develops solutions that benefits the media industry and thereby the European taxpayers as well.

TABLE 8: KEY STAKEHOLDERS, THEIR NEEDS AND CORRESPONDING CONSORTIUM ACTIONS

The third step of the worksession analyzed whether STADIEM would better operate as a network or a community, whether for network focuses on sharing (of best practices) in a high trust network, but a community also adds levels of purpose, ownership, and commitments of social capital. The participants indicated that at this moment, a desirable model for STADIEM is a well-operational network due to its vast differences between members' organizational

structure, focus areas, and outcomes within a holistic mission of boosting media innovation in Europe.

FIGURE 12: RESULTS FROM THE WORKSESSION CONCERNING THE OPERATIONAL STRUCTURE BETWEEN NETWORK AND COMMUNITY

4.4 KEY PRINCIPLES AND AREAS OF IMPROVEMENT

The last and fourth step was to identify key principles for the improvement of tools, processes, and frameworks, especially for the better management of OC2.

The key principles and outcomes identified were as follows:

1. Principle 1: STADIEM's purpose is to support start-ups and scale-ups to foster media innovation in Europe. Accelerating development and co-creation of innovative media solutions that cater to market needs. STADIEM should be a role model for other programs and ecosystems.
2. We will deliver an amazing program where each partner and the consortium as a whole would strive for the best solution by always striving for the highest quality in the approach, tools, processes, and outcomes.
3. We respect roles and foster a collaborative work environment where we are not afraid to speak our mind, ask the right questions, call for help and provide it when needed with curiosity and energy. STADIEM can address the whole media sector or a broad range of challenges within the European media.

The key focus areas for optimization are:

1. Implement a fully functional CRM and calendaring system and not share functions between different tools and platforms - comms, files, reporting, scheduling, documents, analysis, and tasks. Maybe we should have a dedicated one-hour session every month to reflect more on strategy and administration/coordination.
2. More WP-related meetings to discuss action points and updates. One central documentation and communication center. Report and signal in time when an engagement can't be met and propose concrete mitigation actions.
3. Listen to partners and try to understand them well. Listen to others and, understand their needs and backgrounds better, aim for consensus.

The consortium has taken relevant action to foresee the implementation of the agreed principles. The majority of those needs and principles have been addressed by the updated STADIEM framework that clarifies the focus of the program, as well as the STADIEM toolkit in Airtable that is launched for OC2 and improved continuously. Regarding the human and personal factors, there is a consensus in the consortium to increase face-to-face meetings to align with the easing of the COVID19 restrictions, as well as constant tracking of deliverables and progress in the high-intensity period where the OC1 and OC2 phases of the program overlap.

Thus it can be concluded that the consortium has effectively addressed the key pain points indicated in its framework review and delivered solutions to address the areas that need optimization to continue to successfully deliver the STADIEM program.

5 CONCLUSION

The aim of this deliverable was to give an overview of the state of the operational logic and framework of the STADIEM program, including the principles of how to establish a highly operational startup to a corporate entrepreneurship program, and define its key logic and operational model. Specifically, the deliverable advocated for the five-step process, which includes Identifying the core variables of the program (using the SPDC method), Select operational model (using the SPDC method), Design the program components and processes (Toolkits), Deploy & implement the program, Analyze, learn, adapt, and restart if necessary.

It was presented that in order to meet its outcomes and draw from its structural advantages, STADIEM utilizes the startup supplier operational model, which is focused on delivering clear business benefits for the corporate and startup achieved by the high level of scouting and matching of expectations. In doing so, the STADIEM program and its framework have evolved from a well operational “open scaling framework” presented a year ago in deliverable 2.1, as the benefits and outcomes of the program are becoming more visible.

Secondly, the deliverable focused on the lessons learned, which were achieved through a consortium-wide survey to identify relevant tools and processes, as well as an in-depth work session to evaluate the temperature and key parameters in the operation of the consortium.

Both the survey and the work session indicated that whilst operationally successful, improvements were needed in optimizing the workload and efficiency of the collaboration in the consortium. The solution tailored was a dedicated platform operating at Airtable, gathering the key operational functions of the consortium. The platform was developed out of an ideation session and is currently implemented for more effective management of OC2 along with delivering improvements to the consortium's collaboration towards jointly identified principles and priorities.

